

On Thin Ice: The future of glacial runoff in La Paz, Bolivia

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ABSTRACT

Climate change and glacier retreat are threatening the livelihoods of communities that depend on glacial runoff. To better plan for change and develop mitigation strategies, scientists have developed field and computational methods to understand how glacier changes may affect communities. One of the most important methods in determining glacial contribution to future water resources is the use of glacier simulations, which predict the glacier's behavior through time—on the scale of years to decades—given climate and geographical inputs. Current glacier simulators are reliant on climate models to predict meltwater runoff rates, and disagreement in precipitation trends among climate models results in uncertainty in these runoff predictions. This uncertainty is particularly apparent, and important, as these glacier simulators attempt to model glaciers decades into the future. This undergraduate thesis investigates how sensitive glaciers in Bolivia's Cordillera Real are to a range of predicted precipitation trends, and what the implications are for glacial runoff to La Paz and El Alto, Bolivia. Glacial runoff is simulated using the Open Global Glacier Model (OGGM) using climate inputs from 10 Global Climate Models (GCMs) to predict glacier runoff change between 2020 and 2100. Results show that uncertainties in estimates of annual and seasonal runoff result from uncertainties in climate models. The greatest predicted uncertainties among runoff components come from uncertainties in precipitation, rather than from glacier melt. Additionally, seasonal runoff is projected to contribute less water to the cities in the dry season and its shoulder months due to an almost complete loss of glacier melt. This has important implications for the cities' management of water resources. The results of this thesis support that climate models for high mountain regions should be improved to better project precipitation.

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TABLE OF CONTENTS

ABSTRACT	2
ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS	3
CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	5
1.1 BACKGROUND.....	5
1.2 CHARACTERISTICS OF GLACIERS AND GLACIAL RUNOFF	8
1.3 SETTING AND REGIONAL CONTEXT.....	12
1.4 CHANGING TEMPERATURES, CHANGING PRECIPITATION PATTERNS	16
1.5 INTRODUCTION TO CLIMATE AND GLACIER MODELING	17
CHAPTER 2: METHODS.....	21
2.1 SOFTWARE	21
2.2 BASIN DELINEATION IN QGIS.....	21
2.3 GLACIER SELECTION AND MODEL INITIALIZATION	22
2.4 MODEL CALIBRATION.....	25
2.5 FUTURE PROJECTIONS	26
2.6 ANALYSIS	28
CHAPTER 3: RESULTS	29
3.1 ICE VOLUME	29
3.2 ANNUAL RUNOFF	32
3.3 SEASONAL RUNOFF	36
CHAPTER 4: DISCUSSION.....	42
4.1 ICE VOLUME DECREASES OVER TIME.....	42
4.2 TOTAL RUNOFF DECREASES RAPIDLY, EXPLAINED BY CHANGE IN ANNUAL RUNOFF COMPONENTS	42
4.3 PROJECTIONS OF SEASONAL RUNOFF SHOW DECREASE IN GLACIER MELT, INCREASE IN RUNOFF UNCERTAINTY	44
4.4 IMPLICATIONS FOR LA PAZ AND EL ALTO.....	45
4.5 IMPLICATIONS FOR UNDERSTANDING PRECIPITATION UNCERTAINTY	47
4.6 PROJECT LIMITATIONS	48
4.7 POSSIBLE FUTURE WORK.....	49
CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION	51
SUPPLEMENTARY ELECTRONIC INFORMATION.....	52
REFERENCES	53

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 Background

Glacier runoff is an important source of freshwater for communities worldwide. 26% of the world's land surface is covered by non-polar glacierized drainage basins which provide water resources for 1/3 of the world's population (Beniston, 2003; Huss & Hock, 2018). Mountainous regions are particularly important sources of freshwater, where the runoff per unit area is two times higher than in lowland areas (Viviroli et al., 2011). Glaciers contribute significantly to this runoff, particularly in arid basins (Kaser et al., 2010). Glacial runoff changes seasonally and can be a buffer against drought in dry summer months (Ayala et al., 2020; Huss and Hock, 2018). Runoff seasonality is particularly important to agricultural productivity, as it provides water for irrigation across the dry season (Bury et al., 2011). As such, glaciers are a vital resource for communities that rely on runoff as an annual and seasonal water resource.

Glaciers are also valuable indicators of climate change (Beniston, 2003). The Summary for Policymakers from the most recent Assessment Report (AR6) of the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change (IPCC) indicates that changes in temperature and precipitation have resulted in global glacier retreat since the 1950s that is unprecedented in the last 2000 years (IPCC, 2021). Climate change has impacted—and will continue to impact—glacier volume, runoff, and seasonality. It is also projected that alpine glaciers globally will lose between 22 and 57 percent of their mass within the next 30 years (Hock et al., 2019a). Moreover, areas with smaller glaciers and less ice cover, such as the tropical Andes and European Alps, could lose up to 80% of glacier mass under the most severe climate scenarios based on unmitigated emissions. Correspondingly, large reductions in runoff are also expected, particularly in regions of central Asia and the Andes (Huss and Hock, 2018). Runoff seasonality is changing as glaciers retreat, which is significant

for water resources on a seasonal scale (Ultee et al., 2022; Vuille et al., 2008). The decrease in glacier mass from global warming will have significant implications for downstream communities, affecting drinking water access (Chevallier et al., 2011; Vergara et al., 2007), agricultural productivity (Hock et al., 2019a; Bury et al., 2011), hydroelectric power (Bradley et al., 2006), and tourism (Kaenzig et al., 2016).

The scientific community has developed field and computational methods to understand glaciological, hydrologic, and climatic changes. One of the most important methods used to estimate glacial contribution to future water resources over various time scales is the use of models, which simulate the glacier's behavior through time given climatic and geographic inputs. However, glacial runoff projected by models is subject to poorly understood uncertainties due to uncertainty in future climate inputs, particularly precipitation variability (Lee et al., 2021).

In this project, I seek to address uncertainties in runoff quantification by investigating how simulated annual and seasonal glacier runoff in mountain regions responds to precipitation variability. Specifically, this work is a case study focused on the cities of La Paz and El Alto, Bolivia, in the arid Altiplano region of the Andes. These neighboring cities have a combined population of approximately 1,908,000 as of 2022, and are growing rapidly (United Nations, 2022). The glaciology of this region has been historically less studied than regions of the southern Andes (Fernández and Mark, 2016). Additionally, these cities are particularly dependent on glaciers as a water resource; according to a study by Soruco et al. (2015), approximately 15% of annual water resources and 27% of dry season resources for the La Paz metropolitan areas were sourced from glacier runoff, calculated on an annual scale between 1963 and 2006. In the past decade, climatic changes and increased water demand have subjected the cities to water shortages. During 2016, the Bolivian government declared a state of emergency

when a strong El Niño event plunged the cities into drought (Kinouchi et al., 2019). As the demand for water grows and the climate changes, the future of the region's water resources becomes less certain.

To investigate the variability in simulated annual and seasonal glacier runoff for the remaining decades of the 21st century in the watersheds of La Paz and El Alto, Bolivia, I use the Open Global Glacier Model (OGGM). OGGM is an open-source model developed to simulate historic and future glacier change globally (Maussion et al., 2019). I identify glaciated basins in the La Paz region and use OGGM to model and analyze an ensemble of glacier responses to variable precipitation parameters, reflecting a changing climate. I analyze model output on an annual and seasonal scale to understand how a range of possibilities for future precipitation may affect runoff supply. I seek to determine how glaciers reflect changes in precipitation forcing, identifying whether glacier runoff variability is amplified, reduced, or sees little change in the changing climate. These data are also used to define the range of projected annual and seasonal runoff in the future.

The urgency of climate change and alarming rate of glacier retreat provide significant motivation to study glacier runoff with a modeling approach, which allows for predictions of future runoff trends in a warming climate (Hock et al., 2019a). This project addresses the relationship between glacier models and precipitation uncertainty, and how this impacts glacier runoff predictions. This can be an important tool to study the effects of the changing climate on glacier runoff and how that impacts communities. This study adds to previous literature (Soruco et al., 2015; Vergara et al., 2007) investigating glacier runoff for La Paz and seeks to address the precipitation-related uncertainties for quantifying future runoff using a modeling approach. This project has the potential to enhance knowledge on climate risks, impacts, and their consequences

for communities, which is key to implementing and sustaining adaptation (IPCC, 2022). Finally, the modeling approach employed here can be applied to any alpine glaciated regions, providing a framework for global glacier runoff modeling in other critical mountain areas.

In the rest of this chapter, I address how glaciers interact with their landscapes and a changing climate, and how precipitation variability impacts uncertainty in future climate predictions. First, I discuss glacier characteristics and interactions between glaciers and their environments. Next, I introduce the study region of La Paz, Bolivia. This includes a detailed introduction to the geographic, hydrologic, and socioeconomic conditions of the study area. Then, I identify how climate and glacier models can be used to investigate how glaciers respond to changing environments, and what their limitations are. Here, I focus on the uncertainty that comes from variability in future precipitation predictions. Finally, I introduce the glacier model used in this study and provide an overview of glacier modeling.

1.2 Characteristics of glaciers and glacial runoff

To understand the interactions between glaciers and communities, it is important to identify the characteristics of glaciers and how they evolve. As defined by van der Veen (2013), glaciers are masses of compact, perennial ice that deform under the influence of their weight and gravity, flowing down surface gradients from higher to lower elevations. They gain mass through accumulation processes occurring at higher altitudes. The dominant accumulation process is precipitation. Here, I define precipitation as solid or liquid water particles that originate in the atmosphere, including rain, snow, sleet, and other hydrometeors. Mass is lost during ablation, in which water is lost as meltwater runoff, sublimation to the atmosphere, or icebergs calved from the glacier front. The combined processes of accumulation and ablation determine a glacier's

mass balance, which is important in understanding how a glacier's mass fluctuates. When the ablation from a glacier is greater than its accumulation, the glacier will retreat, as it is losing more mass than it is gaining. Conversely, a glacier will advance when it accumulates more mass than is ablated. When glaciers begin to retreat, they tend to produce more runoff, as there is more melting occurring. Following Huss and Hock (2018), I define runoff as all the water that originates within the initially glacierized area, which includes glacier melt and liquid precipitation. As a glacier retreats, annual runoff increases over time until it reaches a certain point that glaciologists call 'peak runoff', after which runoff levels decrease due to diminishing glacier mass (Huss and Hock, 2018).

Glacier dynamics of mass balance and ice flow are non-linear, meaning glaciers do not respond immediately to climate fluctuations, but rather respond over a longer time scale to inter-annual variability (Huston et al., 2021). Glaciers reflect the effects of many atmospheric variables in their mass balance, which allows for delays in their response time to a changing climate (Huybers & Roe, 2009; Oerlemans, 2001). This response time is typically seen on a decadal to centennial scale, meaning glaciers act as low-pass filters of climate that respond to more long-term variability events (Huston et al., 2021; Balco, 2009). As such, the advance or retreat of a glacier does not reflect a single year's climate but is a response to cumulative forcings from many years (Huybers & Roe, 2009). Importantly, this suggests that runoff variability may not be linearly related to precipitation variability.

The glaciers studied in this thesis are tropical glaciers, which are found at high elevations and often have high fluctuations in ablation and accumulation due to their small size and large seasonal changes in cloud cover and precipitation (Rabatel et al., 2013; Sicart et al., 2011). The lowest elevations of the glaciers experience ablation almost year-round due to climate conditions

in the tropics (Soruco et al., 2015). Since tropical glaciers are located within low latitudes, the period of maximum precipitation corresponds with the summer months, during which snow and ice are accumulating at higher altitudes and ice is ablating at lower altitudes (Chevallier et al., 2011). In the months leading up to the wet season (August-December), these glaciers often see the highest rates of runoff due to increased solar radiation and decreases in glacier albedo (surface reflectivity). During the dry season, sublimation plays a key role in glacier mass balance, as the energy supplied by solar radiation is used to sublimate snow and ice rather than to produce melt from the glacier (Wagnon et al., 1999). In this project, I do not calculate glacier mass loss from sublimation due to limitations in glacier models (Section 4.6; Marzeion et al., 2012).

Because of their capacity to retain snow and ice perennially, glaciers are important for water storage. There are two reasons for this: First, orographic lifting tends to enhance precipitation in the high-altitude regions where glaciers are found, such that glaciers receive more precipitation than the surrounding lowlands. Second, low temperatures at high altitudes allow freeze-on and delay the release of water (Immerzeel et al., 2020). Runoff fluctuates seasonally, with glaciers losing more mass to runoff during the hot and dry season when precipitation-derived runoff is low (Chevallier et al., 2011; Immerzeel et al., 2020). As such, glaciers can act as buffers of drought during the dry season, particularly in moderately glaciated, arid basins such as those in the Andes (Ultee et al., 2022).

Figure 1. Map of the study area showing watershed basins for the cities of La Paz and El Alto (labeled La Paz City). The inset shows the location of the study area in red within South America. Glaciers (blue) are found along the peaks of the Cordillera Real and feed rivers and lakes at lower elevations.

1.3 Setting and regional context

The study area of this project encompasses the cities of La Paz and El Alto and the surrounding watersheds (Figure 1). These neighboring cities are in western Bolivia on the Andean Altiplano, an arid plateau along the western Andes. In this thesis, the two cities are often collectively referred to as La Paz for the sake of brevity. At just over 3600 meters above sea level, La Paz is the highest administrative capital in the world (Arbona and Kohl, 2004). The two cities have a combined population of almost 2 million people, a number which is expected to rise in coming decades (Kinouchi et al., 2019; United Nations, 2022). This region has a strong reliance on high-altitude water stocks—including glaciers and lakes—that complement limited precipitation resources in the arid region (Bradley et al., 2006). To the northeast of the metropolitan area lies the Cordillera Real, a mountain range with peaks rising over 6,000 meters. The Cordillera Real contains 11% of the world's tropical glaciers and 55% of Bolivian glaciers (Jordan, 1991). The small glaciers that are found within the Cordillera Real lie between 4,000 and 6,400 meters above sea level (Seehaus et al., 2019). Most of the cities' water resources come from these mountains. The La Paz city water system draws from five mountain drainage areas, four of which contain important water reservoirs: Tuni-Condoriri, Milluni, Hampaturi, and Incachaca (Figure 1; Soruco et al., 2015). Pipelines connect these basins to the city of La Paz and water is collected in three drinking water treatment plants: El Alto station, Achachicala station, and Pampahasi station (Kinouchi et al., 2019; Soruco et al., 2015). The Choqueyapu river basin contains no reservoirs but provides seasonal streamflow to the system (Kinouchi et al., 2019).

In their 2015 article on glacier runoff for La Paz, Soruco et al. describe the characteristics of the region's climate. Mean annual conditions for the La Paz region are characterized by small differences in seasonal temperatures and high precipitation seasonality. Between 2000 and 2007,

average mean temperatures in La Paz ranged from 2°C in the austral winter to 10°C in the austral summer. In a study of climate trends in Bolivia between 1960 and 2009, temperatures rose by 0.1°C per decade, with stronger increases in the Andes (Seiler, Hutjes, & Kabat, 2013). The altiplano region has distinct wet and dry seasons, with the height of the wet season between January and March and the dry season between May and August (Sorucu et al., 2015). Wet season precipitation accounts for 90% of the annual precipitation within the Cordillera Real (Francou et al., 2003). Large-scale interannual climate phenomena like the El Niño Southern Oscillation (ENSO) are particularly important in this region, as studies have shown that strong El Niño years are correlated with less precipitation and a delay in the wet season (Francou, 2004; Sicart et al., 2005). Between 1960 and 2009, year-round temperatures in the Bolivian Andes were shown to be higher during El Niño events than non-El Niño years (Seiler, Hutjes, & Kabat, 2013). Additionally, the same area saw drier conditions with more variable precipitation during austral summer months (December-February) because of El Niño. ENSO episodes are drivers of drought events, with the most recent important drought in La Paz occurring during 2016 (Kinouchi et al., 2019; Marengo et al., 2017).

Tropical glaciers typically accumulate mass during the wet season and lose mass during the dry season. This creates a seasonal buffering effect, in which the glaciers of the Cordillera Real provide significant water resources during dry months due to their capacity to store water during the wet season and release it during the dry season (Ribstein et al., 1995). According to the study by Sorucu et al. (2015), glaciers in the catchment areas surrounding La Paz contributed approximately 15% of annual water resources between 1993 and 2006. The glacial contribution to water resources was especially important in the dry season, accounting for 27% of seasonal flow at that time. Calculations of runoff between 1963 and 2006 show that glacier runoff did not

change significantly, despite a 50% reduction in glacier area within the Cordillera Real (Soruco et al., 2009). This indicates that higher melt rates were able to compensate for the loss of glacier area and that peak levels of runoff may have been reached (Huss and Hock, 2018; Soruco et al., 2015). Assuming the complete disappearance of glaciers in the Cordillera Real, total runoff to La Paz is projected to diminish by 12% annually: 9% during the wet season, and 24% during the dry season (Soruco et al., 2015). Rising populations and diminishing resources put La Paz in a precarious position. The water demand for these cities is expected to increase by 15 to 53% between 2011 and 2036, while projected water supply shows reductions due to changes in glacier runoff and precipitation (Buytaert and De Bièvre, 2012; Kinouchi et al., 2019). The projected mismatch between demand and availability is a strong motivation for better constraining the uncertainty in modeled output, with the objective of helping managers assess and respond to changes. Model projections of runoff seasonality changes will be vital for the identification and implementation of management strategies in a response to changing resources.

Bolivia is one of the poorest countries in South America, and thus is highly vulnerable to environmental changes, which will be exacerbated in the coming years (Winters, 2012). In a changing climate, limitations in water infrastructure are enhanced, which is particularly evident in recent struggles with water use and drought (Kinouchi et al., 2019). The most extreme drought in the last 25 years in La Paz occurred in 2016 following a strong ENSO event (Kinouchi et al., 2019). In response to a loss of 92-99% of regional reservoir capacities, the Bolivian government declared a state of emergency, resulting in water rationing across La Paz and El Alto (Rivero et al., 2020). The near collapse of the water system in 2016 was a result of drought as well as water system mismanagement and fragility of the system (Botton and Urquieta, 2020). ENSO rainfall variability is expected to become amplified by the mid-21st century, which will have strong

implications on annual and decadal runoff for La Paz (IPCC, 2021). Water scarcity coupled with a projected increase in demand of water sources in the coming decades necessitates the identification and projection of future water resources for La Paz (Kinouchi et al., 2019).

The loss of glacier mass and expected decline in glacier meltwater in the Cordillera Real have significant implications for downstream communities, affecting drinking water access, hydroelectric capacities, agricultural production, and the tourism industry (Rangecroft et al., 2013). Changing runoff quantities can affect water costs and access for communities, potentially resulting in shortages and conflict that will be particularly evident in the dry season (Painter, 2008; Vergara et al., 2007). Hydropower is a major source of energy within the Andes that relies on glacier runoff to fill reservoirs (Bradley et al., 2006). La Paz is dependent on hydroelectric power from surrounding catchment basins for a significant amount of its energy resources (Painter, 2008). If hydroelectric power is strongly affected by declining rates of glacier runoff, it is probable that the community would shift towards fossil fuels (Bradley et al., 2006).

Agricultural production in the La Paz region is also expected to change with the warming climate. Currently, seasonal glacier runoff provides year-round water for agriculture (Vergara et al., 2007). As the climate warms, it will be possible to cultivate land at higher altitudes, leading to potential competition between stakeholders as water demand increases and supply decreases (Chevallier et al., 2011). Another economic activity that is impacted by climate change and glacier reduction in this area is the tourism industry. An example is Chacaltaya glacier, which used to be a popular tourist destination as the highest ski area in the world. However, the glacier disappeared completely in 2009 as a result of warming temperatures (Kaenzig et al., 2016). Changes in environmental conditions will have consequences for tourist activities and economic revenue in this area.

1.4 Changing temperatures, changing precipitation patterns

In a changing climate, there is greater variability in projected precipitation patterns (Arias et al, 2021). General scientific consensus shows that mean precipitation is increasing, driven by increases in moisture from a warming climate (Allen and Ingram, 2002). However, projections of precipitation are variable and region-dependent, relying on present-day precipitation simulations to predict future precipitation changes (Allen and Ingram, 2002; Wood et al., 2021). The 6th Assessment Report by the Intergovernmental Panel on Climate Change projects that precipitation patterns globally will become more variable in the future, and that extreme precipitation events will become more common (2021).

Historically, it has been difficult to detect long-term changes in precipitation in the Andes due to the range's intrinsic variability, which is a result of significant elevation differences and air/wind anomalies (Vuille and Keimig, 2004). The applications of these limitations in climate models are developed in the following section. Literature suggests that Bolivia has seen a slight decrease in precipitation during the 20th century (Vuille et al., 2003). Climate models show varying projections for the sign of precipitation changes in Bolivia, with some projecting positive changes in mean precipitation and others projecting negative changes (Douveille et al., 2021). In addition to long-term precipitation changes, the tropical Andes are significantly affected by interannual and decadal scale precipitation, particularly the El Niño Southern Oscillation (Viviroli et al., 2011). ENSO's dynamical complexity and multi-annual nature makes it difficult to model in future scenarios (Collins et al., 2005). As such, model parameters make it difficult to include this phenomenon in climate and glacier models.

Current glacier models rely on precipitation parameters to project glacier changes, and as such, it is important that projected precipitation reflects the most accurate range of future possibilities (Lehner et al., 2019). Previous work has focused on global-scale uncertainty of climate and glacier models, but regional variations in climate make it difficult to apply these global-scale conclusions to regional-scale projections (Lehner et al., 2019; Ultee et al., 2022). In this project, I address uncertainty in regional modeled glacier runoff using varying precipitation inputs used to simulate the variability in projected precipitation over time.

1.5 Introduction to climate and glacier modeling

Climate and glacier models are important tools for understanding how glaciers will respond to future environmental conditions. Soruco et al. (2015) were able to calculate present-day runoff in La Paz using historic climate records, which do not consider evolving climate conditions in the future. In-situ measurements can be important tools, yet they are limited in their ability to project future environmental changes and characteristics (Radić and Hock, 2014). Additionally, in-situ measurements are sparse for the glaciers within the Cordillera Real (Gärtner-Roer et al., 2019). In this thesis, I attempt to supplement the understanding of glacier runoff to La Paz using a modeling approach.

Climate models are useful for analyzing future climate scenarios and are used as inputs into glacier models. Applications of climate models include simulating historical climate, predicting future climate variability and change, and making global and regional projections (Flato et al., 2013). The base of a climate model is a Global Climate Model (GCM) which simulates the earth's major climate system processes on a coarse grid encompassing the entire globe (Flato et al., 2013; Chen et al., 2021). GCMs are derived from fundamental laws of physics

and mathematics and are further approximated with climate system parameters (Randall et al., 2007).

To simulate possible global climate futures, the research community develops and uses scenarios, which are used to improve our understanding of interactions between the climate system, ecosystems, and human activities (Moss et al., 2010). Global Climate Models use these scenarios, or pathways, as inputs to drive global climate projections. In 2010, Moss and others proposed four pathways to represent variations in climate parameters that simulate possible global climate futures. These Representative Concentration Pathways (RCPs) represent trajectories of greenhouse gas concentrations for the year 2100 that are defined for a range of radiative forcing values. Radiative forcing, measured in watts per square meter (W/m^2), is a widely used metric for climate change that represents the change in Earth's top-of-atmosphere energy balance caused by natural or anthropogenic perturbations (Myhre et al., 2013; Moss et al., 2010). The RCPs are defined at 2.6, 4.5, 6, and $8.5 \text{ W}/\text{m}^2$ of radiative forcing, with the 'smallest' climate change occurring in the RCP2.6 scenario and the most significant climate change occurring in the RCP8.5 scenario. In 2012, Taylor and others decided that RCP scenarios would be used as forcings for concentration or emission scenarios for the fifth phase of the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project (CMIP5), a multi-model simulation exercise whose output is summarized in the IPCC's 5th annual report. Use of these Representative Concentration Pathways is the standard method to explore multiple possible futures in climate simulations.

Climate models are limited in their physical and computational capacities, as any computational model is an imperfect representation of the real world (Chen et al., 2021). Precipitation and temperature trends vary substantially by GCM, and since GCMs make global predictions, it can be difficult to downscale projections to local and regional scales, particularly

in areas with high and variable topography (Hock et al., 2019b; Flato et al., 2013). Regional scale climate models also exist but are computationally expensive and have a limited spatial scale (Buytaert et al., 2010; Van de Wal & Wild, 2001). Thus, it can be difficult to model small-scale, regional changes such as precipitation in the tropical Andes (Buytaert et al., 2010). The coarse spatial resolution of climate models is particularly consequential in mountain regions, where changes in elevation correspond with significant changes in climate, particularly for temperature and precipitation (Buytaert et al., 2010). Moreover, it can be difficult for models to represent orographic enhancement of precipitation, leading to high precipitation uncertainties in mountainous regions (Strandberg & Lind, 2021).

Glacier models use mathematical and physical concepts to simulate how glaciers have changed over time, to project future glacier dynamics, and to understand underlying concepts of glacial processes (Fernández and Mark, 2016; Maussion et al., 2019). Climate models provide climate forcings to these glacier simulations to determine how glaciers will evolve over time as precipitation and temperature change in different RCP scenarios (Radić and Hock, 2014). For this thesis, I required that the chosen glacier model have an existing framework for calculating runoff, be open source, and be applicable to dozens of glaciers at basin scale (a “large-scale” or “global” glacier model). Many global glacier models exist, yet only three models contain a framework for calculating glacier runoff: the Open Global Glacier Model (OGGM; Maussion et al., 2019), the Python Glacier Evolution Model (PyGEM; Rounce et al., 2020), and the Global Glacier Evolution Model (GloGEM; Huss & Hock, 2015). Of these models, I selected OGGM due to its applications at a basin-scale for glacier modeling and its open-source access.

The Open Global Glacier Model is an open-source glacier modeling framework that is written in python and is openly accessible through GitHub (Maussion et al., 2019). In addition to

the aforementioned reasons, OGGM is useful for this thesis due to its calculations of glacier mass balance that account for ice deformation and flow. Other models calculate glacier mass balance based solely off altitude measurements and assume no flow, which tends to overestimate glacial water storage in some cases and underestimate it in others (van de Wal and Wild, 2001; van der Veen, 2013). OGGM is also well suited for this thesis because it provides a self-consistent method to track runoff from multiple sources in glaciated catchments. The tool built in to OGGM partitions runoff from glacier melt, snow and ice melt off the glacier, and precipitation on and off the glacier. My workflow applies OGGM in a Jupyter Lab environment to update and execute code for the glacier model.

For this study, I select glaciers within the five relevant watershed basins surrounding La Paz using QGIS and OGGM (Figure 1). I supply glacier data, including a unique ID, area, and grid geometry, to model functions that compute each glacier's mass balance and flow dynamics at monthly time steps. I simulate the glacier response to climate boundary conditions computed from General Circulation Models and forced with four RCP scenarios. I downscale climate data to the region of interest and the resulting data are held in glacier directories. Next, I compute hydrologic output on an annual and seasonal scale at each glacier using the modeled glacier directories. I then analyze trends of glacier change on a seasonal and annual scale from 2020 to 2100, calculating mean runoff values as well as RCP and GCM spread. This workflow is further explained in the next chapter.

CHAPTER 2: METHODS

2.1 Software

In this thesis, I used the Python programming language in a Jupyter notebook to adapt and execute the Open Global Glacier Model (OGGM), an open-source model built in python. (Maussion et al., 2019). I used version 1.5.3 of OGGM, released on April 4, 2022 (Maussion et al., 2022). Within my modeling workflow, I used packages including: xarray for multidimensional analysis, numpy for common mathematical operations, pandas for analysis, geopandas and shapely.geometry for shapefile importing and geometrical analysis, and seaborn and matplotlib for visualization. I also used the software QGIS, an open-source GIS platform, to delineate basins and for geographic visualizations. The Jupyter notebooks and code that are associated with this project can be accessed through Github (see Supplementary Electronic Information)

2.2 Basin delineation in QGIS

I relied on previous work studying the hydrologic sources for La Paz to determine which watersheds should be included in my study. In their 2015 article on La Paz's glacial water resources, Soruco et al. define four glaciated basins that contribute to La Paz: Tuni-Condoriri, Milluni, Hampaturi, and Incachaca. Another study by Kinouchi et al. in 2019 includes the Choqueyapu basin in addition to the other four. This basin was not included by Soruco et al. since it does not contain a water reservoir. However, it does contribute fluvially to the city of La Paz. In this project, I used all five catchment basins to select glaciers whose runoff could contribute to La Paz water resources (Figure 2).

Basin outlines from previous literature are not readily available online; as such, I identified matching basin outlines using the HydroSHEDS dataset (Lehner & Grill, 2013). I chose this dataset because it is freely available for scientific use, includes global data, has a 15 arc-second spatial resolution, and contains 12 levels of sub basins. Once I identified which basins to use, I selected their geographic outlines using the HydroBASINS database, a subset of the HydroSHEDS database. This database consists of shapefile layers depicting global basin boundaries at different scales. For this project, I selected sub-basins in South America from level 12, which is the smallest basin scale available. This level was chosen due to its comparable scale to the basins delineated in previous literature.

To select the five basins that contribute to La Paz, I imported the level 12 HydroBASINS dataset for South America into QGIS and manually selected the five basins around La Paz by visual comparison with maps in previous studies (Soruco et al., 2015; Kinouchi et al., 2019). I then consolidated these basins into one vector to be read into the glacier model.

2.3 Glacier selection and model initialization

To initiate the model for the study area, I selected glaciers within the delineated catchment basins. Global glacier outline data is available through the Randolph Glacier Inventory (RGI) and is contributed to by the glaciological community (RGI Consortium, 2017). I used glacier outlines defined by RGI version 6, released in 2017, which refer to the glacier's outline in the year 2000. Each glacier is assigned a unique identifier, called an RGI ID, which is used to select glaciers to simulate with OGGM.

I used the merged basin shapefile described in section 2.2 to select glaciers whose RGI outlines intersect watersheds draining to La Paz. I selected 35 glaciers surrounding La Paz with a

total glacier area of 26.27 km² (Figure 2a). Eight of these glaciers were unable to be modeled by OGGM due to uncertainties in input data. According to OGGM documentation, approximately 3.1% of glaciers worldwide cannot be modeled by OGGM, with low latitude regions accounting for the second highest percentage of the errors (Maussion et al., 2019). Among the OGGM-invalid glaciers at low latitudes, the most common obstacle (96% of cases) is insurmountable discrepancies between the climate input data and glacier mass balance module. This can arise due to missing processes within the OGGM mass balance model, which does not incorporate mass loss from sublimation. I address this limitation further in section 4.6 of the Discussion. In total, invalid glaciers accounted for 2.85 km² of the total basin glacier area of 26.27 km² and are distributed evenly across the study area (Figure 2b). Due to their even distribution and small area relative to the other glaciers, for this thesis I removed the eight invalid glaciers from my analysis and continued with the remaining 27 glaciers.

Figure 2. Map of the study area showing (a) all glaciers (dark blue) within watershed basins (light blue) and (b) all glaciers (dark blue) with invalid glaciers (red).

2.4 Model calibration

Once I selected the 27 valid glaciers and their RGI IDs, I initiated glacier preprocessing, which sets up the geographical input data for each glacier (this includes glacier outlines and local topography) and determines glacier flow lines (Maussion et al., 2019). This information is stored within a glacier directory, which stores the input and output from model runs unique to each glacier. Following preprocessing, the next stage of the project included three important steps: defining the glaciers' evolution using historical climate data, initializing the model's projected climate using a given Global Climate Model (GCM), and running the simulation using the GCM-defined climate projection to quantify runoff.

Simulating a glacier's evolution using historical climate data is important to ensure the glacier model applies at the individual glacier level. This step serves to calibrate the mass balance model using historical climate data, which sets glacier-specific parameters to use in future simulations. An appropriate combination of parameters is chosen so that the glacier is near equilibrium at the beginning of the study period, which prevents anomalous behavior in the transition between historical and future glacier modeling. In order to do this, the geometry (area, volume, and shape) and evolution of the glaciers must be spun up from a given year. For the historical run, I selected a fixed geometry spinup year of 1990, which is 10 years before the nominal date of the outline (2000; RGI Consortium, 2017). For modeling purposes, this documentation year, the RGI date, should be when the glacier reaches equilibrium. This is standard for other simulations run with OGGM (Maussion et al., 2019).

For the historical run as well as for future runs, I used the OGGM task `run_with_hydro`, which simulates a set of glaciers under a given climate scenario and outputs an array of glacier variables including runoff (separated by source) for each time step.

OGGM uses the Climate Research Unit (CRU) climate dataset in the historical climate run (Harris et al., 2014; Maussion et al., 2019). The resulting data from the historical climate run is an array with three dimensions: *time*, *rgi_id*, and *month*. These dimensions include variables for each glacier—represented by RGI ID—on an annual and monthly scale. For this simulation, the annual dimension represents data from 1990 to 2021. For this project, the most important output variables are: melt on glacier, melt off glacier, liquid precipitation on glacier, and liquid precipitation off glacier. Other important variables include glacier area and volume for the simulated period. This OGGM task computes runoff on the initially glaciated area, which is equivalent to the hypothetical runoff measured at a fixed-gage station at the glacier’s terminus (Huss & Hock, 2018). The melt on glacier variable is the calculated melt from on the glacier, whereas the melt off glacier variable is the calculated seasonal snow melt from the non-glaciated area within the area of interest. Similarly, liquid precipitation on glacier is the amount of liquid precipitation (i.e., rain) that falls on the glacier’s surface and liquid precipitation off glacier is the amount of liquid precipitation that falls off the glacier but within the initially glaciated catchment. For this thesis, I summed the liquid precipitation on and off glacier to represent liquid precipitation over the entire area of interest. Output from this historical run is stored to connect future projections with the past conditions that initiate them (Marzeion et al., 2020).

2.5 Future projections

After performing the historical climate run and calculating historical runoff data, I used a selection of ten Global Climate Models (GCMs) to project future runoff for La Paz. In this project, I used an ensemble of GCMs to represent precipitation variability since GCMs produce a wide range of projected precipitation (Hock et al., 2019b). The GCMs that are used in

	RCP 2.6	RCP 4.5	RCP 6.0	RCP 8.5
CCSM4	X	X	X	X
CNRM-CM5	X	X		X
CSIRO-Mk3-6-0	X	X	X	X
CanESM2	X	X		X
GFDL-CM3	X	X	X	X
GFDL-ESM2G	X	X	X	X
GISS-E2-R	X	X	X	X
IPSL-CM5A-LR	X	X	X	X
MPI-ESM-LR	X	X		X
NorESM1-M	X	X	X	X

Table 1. List of 10 GCMs selected from the CMIP5 glacier intercomparison project and the RCP scenario availability of each. Note that three models do not include RCP6.0, and thus there were 37 total model realizations.

this project are detailed in Table 1. I selected Ten GCMs from the Coupled Model Intercomparison Project Phase 5 (CMIP5) ensemble (Taylor et al., 2012) based on the availability of multiple RCP scenarios, facility of use within OGGM, and the choice in previous model intercomparisons (Hock et al., 2019b; Marzeion et al., 2020).

For each run, I needed to take global climate data from the CRU dataset and scale the data down to a regional level (Harris et al., 2014). To do this, I imported climate data from the OGGM server hosted by the University of Bremen. This includes precipitation and temperature data specific to each GCM. I then applied the GCM anomalies, in this case precipitation and temperature biases, to the baseline local climatology defined using the gridded CRU climate dataset (Harris et al., 2014; Maussion et al., 2019). The model then uses the interpolated climate data for each GCM to calculate glacier mass balance, which is important for simulating the glacier’s evolution. Using this climate data, I ran the OGGM task `run_with_hydro` for each GCM and scenario. To initiate this task, I input the GCM climate data and used the equilibrated geometry and mass balance conditions from the historical run as initial conditions within the

model. The output from the runoff simulation includes the same variables but over a different time scale. Here, there are 82 annual time measurements, which start in 2020 and end in 2101. Finally, I compiled the runoff data from each glacier into four datasets for each GCM, one for each RCP scenario. In total, I repeated this process for each GCM and for four RCP scenarios. With three GCMs lacking data for RCP6.0, there are 37 simulations total.

2.6 Analysis

With the compiled runoff data for each glacier, GCM, and RCP scenario, I calculated basin-wide runoff and analyzed trends using Python. To begin, I summed runoff values of all glaciers to total catchment-scale runoff. The resulting runoff data includes both monthly and annual data from 2020 to 2100 for each GCM and RCP scenario. To characterize uncertainty within runoff projections, I calculated the spread, or range, in projections by RCP scenario and by GCM. For RCP uncertainty, I calculated the range of multi-GCM means at the end of the simulation (year 2100). I calculated inter-GCM spread for each RCP scenario as the range of ten GCM results, taken again from the year 2100. I calculated annual values for volume, total runoff, and runoff by component, and seasonal values of RCP and GCM spread during the month of peak runoff, averaged over the first and last decade of the simulation (2020-2030 and 2090-2100), as well as average month of peak runoff at four time steps across the simulation (2020, 2040, 2060, and 2100). Finally, I plotted the evolution of volume and runoff on different time scales to visually investigate projections.

CHAPTER 3: RESULTS

3.1 Ice volume

Across all RCP scenarios, modeled total ice volume for the 27 glaciers is projected to decrease from 2020 to 2100. As seen in Figure 3, initial multi-GCM mean glacier volume projections for all RCPs are almost identical but diverge towards the end of the simulated period. By 2100, the RCP2.6 scenario shows the least volume loss, the RCP4.5 and RCP6.0 scenarios show intermediate volumes, and the RCP8.5 scenario shows the most volume loss. All RCP scenarios show decreases in ice volume of more than 50% across the simulated period, with 57% of volume lost in RCP2.6 and almost 66% lost in RCP8.5. In an RCP2.6 scenario, glaciers will retain 14% more mass than they would in an RCP8.5 scenario. Across all scenarios, glacier volume decreases rapidly from 2020 until around 2050, when the rate of volume loss begins to even out. The GCM spread of projected volumes is between 0.027 and 0.039 km³ and the RCP spread of projected volumes is 0.04 km³ (Figure 4). These values are comparable, with neither GCM nor RCP dominating the spread in projected ice volume loss.

Figure 3. Multi-GCM mean ice volume for all RCP scenarios from 2020 to 2100. Multi-GCM means are displayed in colored lines corresponding to each RCP scenario. Across all RCPs, ice volume is projected to decrease by more than 50% from the beginning of the simulation to the end.

Figure 4. Multi-GCM ice volume for all RCP scenarios from 2020 to 2100. Volumes for each GCM run are plotted in blue, with multi-GCM means represented by black lines. Across all RCPs, GCM spread remains consistent with little change in spread across the simulated period and across RCP scenarios.

3.2 Annual runoff

Model results project that annual runoff will decrease between 2020 and 2100 across all RCP scenarios (Figure 5). Total mean runoff varies little between RCP scenarios [0.68 Mt at the end of the simulation]. In all scenarios, runoff shows a negative trend, with the most substantial decrease in runoff projected between 2020 and 2040. At the end of the simulation, the spread of values projected by each GCM presents some differences in RCP scenarios, with the least severe warming scenarios showing significantly less spread in GCM values [10.59 Mt] than the most severe RCP scenario [27.45 Mt].

The three primary components of runoff—liquid precipitation, melt on glacier, and melt off glacier—behave differently over the simulated period and show some differences across RCP scenarios (Figure 6a). Liquid precipitation contributes the most to runoff over the simulated period and shows the most inter-GCM spread [8.21 Mt for RCP2.6 and 27.01 Mt for RCP8.5]. Both melt on glacier and melt off glacier have very low inter-GCM spread [0.67 to 1.86 Mt and 0.09 to 3.96 Mt depending on RCP scenario] (Figure 6a).

Liquid precipitation contributes between 62 and 64 percent of water at the beginning of the simulation and between 91 and 97 percent of water at the end, where the lower estimates correspond to RCP 2.6 and 4.5 scenarios and higher estimates correspond to RCP 6.0 and 8.5 scenarios (Figure 6b). In the RCP2.6 and 4.5 scenarios, mean liquid precipitation projections remain consistent across the simulated. Both RCP6.0 and RCP8.5 scenarios show a slight increase in mean liquid precipitation estimates. The spread of GCM values does not change much between the beginning and end of the simulation in all scenarios except RCP8.5, which visually shows a greater spread towards the end of the simulation (Figure 6b).

Figure 5. Multi-GCM total annual runoff for all RCP scenarios from 2020 to 2100. Individual GCM runoff projections are represented by blue lines, with multi-GCM means for each RCP scenario represented by black lines. In all RCP scenarios, runoff decreases over the simulated period, with the most significant change occurring during the first 20 years of the simulation.

Figure 6. Annual multi-GCM comparison plots (row a) of projected runoff by runoff component and individual plots (rows b, c, d) of projected runoff by individual runoff components for each RCP scenario. The second through fourth rows have y-axis scales that are set to best show each component, and thus the second row does not have a 0 on the y-axis. GCM projections are colored by runoff component: liquid precipitation (purple), melt on glacier (red), melt off glacier (orange). Multi-GCM mean values are plotted in black lines.

Moreover, the RCP spreads of projected liquid precipitation [1.70 Mt] and melt on glacier [0.25 Mt] are much smaller than the GCM spreads of the same components. These results show that runoff—in particular, the liquid precipitation component of runoff—is more sensitive to GCM than to RCP scenario.

Projected melt on glacier declines during the simulation period across all RCP scenarios (Figure 6c). During the first 20 years of the simulation, melt on glacier decreases by more than 50% then reaches a stable runoff value just above zero. The inter-GCM spread for melt on glacier is very small and does not vary by RCP scenario to the extent that the liquid precipitation component does [between 0.67 and 1.68 Mt] (Figure 6c). The only scenario with slight variation is RCP8.5, which shows a smaller inter-GCM spread during the last 20 years of the simulation than the other scenarios do [0.90 Mt]. The smaller inter-GCM spread in melt on glacier at the end of the century is likely not an indication of convergence among GCMs, but rather near-total deglaciation of the study area, such that there is very little glacier area available to melt at all.

The third component of runoff, melt off glacier, behaves differently in each RCP scenario, which contrasts to the behavior of the other two components. Figure 6d shows that mean melt off glacier increases in RCP2.6 and has greater GCM spread compared to the other RCP scenarios [3.96 Mt compared to 1.12, 0.66, and 0.09 Mt for RCPs 4.5, 6.0, and 8.5]. The other three RCP scenarios show that melt off glacier increases during the first 10 to 20 years of the simulation, then decreases over the rest of the simulation. In these scenarios, inter-GCM spread is visually higher at the beginning of the simulation than at the end (Figure 6d). Like its melt on glacier behavior, RCP8.5 shows a smaller inter-GCM spread [0.09 Mt] during the last 20 years of the simulation than other scenarios do (Figure 6). I interpret that this reflects a wholesale shift to liquid rather than solid precipitation by the end of the century in RCP 8.5, the warmest

among the climate scenarios I tested; like melt on glacier, there simply is not much snow or ice available to be melted. The study area is very high in elevation (more than 4000m a.s.l.) and in reality, would be more likely than other parts of the GCM grid cell to receive solid precipitation, due to the lapse in atmospheric temperature with elevation (typically 6.5°C per km). I address the issue of precipitation phase further in the Discussion.

3.3 Seasonal runoff

Total seasonal runoff changes across the simulation period with slight differences observed by RCP scenario. More runoff is produced in the beginning of the simulated period than at the end in all RCP scenarios, with the peaks of runoff corresponding to months 12 through 2 and troughs corresponding to months 5 through 8 (Figure 7). In all scenarios, runoff in months 4-6 and months 7-9 is highest in 2020 and decreases to a stable amount in the 3 other plotted years (Figure 7). During the simulation period, the average month during which peak runoff is reached is January, during the height of the wet season (Figure 8). GCM projections of seasonal runoff show substantial variability in runoff peaks across the study period and across RCP scenarios (Figure 8). In the four years represented in Figure 8, the spread of GCM projections in months 5 through 8 is relatively small and changes little over time and RCP. However, the peaks show significant variability in GCM spread, particularly in the RCP8.5 scenario [5.90 Mt in 2020 to 7.98 Mt in 2100]. The RCP spread at the month of peak runoff is consistently smaller than the GCM spread at the same times [1.01 Mt in 2020 to 1.19 Mt in 2100].

Figure 7. Seasonal multi-GCM mean runoff projections for four years within the simulation period and for all RCPs. The average runoff for the four years selected—2020, 2040, 2060, and 2100—are represented by shades of blue, as seen in the legend. Each subplot represents an RCP scenario. Months are plotted on the x axis to best show variation between seasonal runoff peak and trough, beginning with October (10) and ending with September (9).

Figure 8. Seasonal multi-GCM runoff projections with GCM runoff projections for four years within the simulation period and for all RCPs. Each row is a single time slice—2020, 2040, 2060, and 2100, and each column is an RCP scenario. Lines representing GCM projection values are colored by year, with the same symbology as that in Figure 5. Multi-GCM mean values are plotted in black lines. Values of month of peak runoff and GCM spread are shown in the top right of each figure in the following format: [month, spread in Mt].

In the first decade of the simulation, liquid precipitation and melt on glacier provide runoff throughout the year (Figure 9). In September through April, liquid precipitation is the dominant form of runoff in all RCP scenarios. By the end of the simulation, liquid precipitation dominates runoff annually, and the wet-season contribution of melt on and off glacier is negligible. This is supported by Figure 10, which compares the relative contributions of runoff components during the first and last decade of the simulation. At the beginning of the study period, liquid precipitation is the primary contributor between September and April and melt on glacier is the primary contributor during the rest of the year. At the end of the simulation, melt off glacier appears to be the only component that rivals the relative importance of liquid precipitation, although comparison with Figure 9 suggests that this may be less important since runoff is almost zero at this time. Comparing the two components of glacier melt at the end of the simulation, melt off glacier contributes more to runoff in RCP2.6 and RCP4.5 and melt on glacier contributes more in RCP6.0 and RCP8.5. Across RCP scenarios, GCM projections for melt on glacier and melt off glacier vary little (Figure 9). Additionally, there is relatively small inter-GCM spread for these values at both the beginning and end of the simulation compared to the inter-GCM spread of liquid precipitation (Figure 9). At its runoff peak, the inter-GCM spread of liquid precipitation is smallest in the moderate RCP scenarios (4.5 and 6.0). Moreover, the inter-GCM spread increases between the beginning and end of the simulation in all scenarios except RCP2.6 (Figure 9).

Multi-GCM decadal seasonal runoff by runoff component

Figure 9. Average decadal multi-GCM mean seasonal runoff by runoff component for 2020-2030 and 2090 to 2100 for all RCPs. RCP scenarios are plotted in rows, with each column representing a different decade. Values of month of peak runoff and GCM spread, colored by component, are shown in the top right of each figure in the following format: [month, spread in Mt].

Relative seasonal contribution of runoff components

Figure 10. Relative average seasonal contributions of runoff components, averaged over GCMs, for 2020-2030 and 2090-2100. RCP scenarios are plotted by column, with RCP2.6 represented at the top and RCP8.5 represented at the bottom of the figure.

CHAPTER 4: DISCUSSION

4.1 Ice volume decreases over time

Results from my glacier simulations show that glacier volume will decrease during the next 80 years, regardless of RCP scenario or GCM (Figure 3). This total decreasing trend is not unexpected; many studies project decreases in glacier volume worldwide, including in the tropical Andes (Huss & Hock, 2018; Marzeion et al., 2020; Rounce et al., 2023). My model shows that the least volume loss will occur in the RCP2.6 scenario and the greatest loss will occur in the RCP8.5 scenario, which also is to be expected since RCP2.6 is the least severe warming scenario and RCP8.5 is the most severe scenario (IPCC, 2014). By the end of the simulation, it is likely that the remaining glacier volume will be held within glaciers that were largest at the beginning of the simulation (Beniston, 2003; Hock et al., 2019b). The trends in projected volume loss from my model are consistent with larger scale, regional trends in the low latitudes (Hock et al., 2019b; Marzeion et al., 2020).

4.2 Total runoff decreases rapidly, explained by change in annual runoff components

Total annual runoff is projected to diminish substantially within the next 30 years and to reach a state of relative equilibrium as the simulation continues (Figure 5). Across all four RCP scenarios, total runoff decreases, with little trend variation between RCP scenarios ([0.68 Mt], Figure 5). As such, runoff could be expected to behave in similar manners regardless of the climate warming scenario. However, there is substantial inter-GCM spread in projected runoff. My results show few differences between RCP scenarios, suggesting the surprising conclusion that future runoff from glaciated areas around La Paz does not depend strongly on the strength of climate warming. My results do, however, show variation in projections by GCM, suggesting

that temperature and precipitation—the essential forcing variables—vary more per GCM in this region than they do per RCP. This indicates that GCM projections are highly variable, and they have a difficult time projecting the future climate in this area. Finally, since total runoff is expected to decrease over the simulated period, it is probable that these small tropical glaciers have already reached “peak runoff”, as defined by Huss and Hock (2018).

I investigated the individual components of runoff computed by the model to identify changes in runoff patterns and possible causes for the decrease in total annual runoff. Annual runoff is dominated by liquid precipitation, with high variability in projected quantities by GCM. Melt that originates on the glacier originally contributes significantly to runoff but declines rapidly during the first 30 years of the simulation (Figure 6). This decline in melt on glacier explains the decline in total runoff and likely is an effect of decreasing glacier volume, as there is less available water stored in the glaciers.

Liquid precipitation over the glacier area varies relatively little between RCP scenarios, although there is a slight increase in mean projected liquid precipitation in RCP6.0 and RCP8.5. This is likely a result of a phase change of precipitation associated with the warmer climate scenario. In a less severe scenario such as RCP2.6, there is less warming, and as such the precipitation that falls on the glacier area is more likely to include snowfall, which contributes to the melt off glacier component. This is likely why the melt off glacier component shows a positive trend in RCP2.6 and decreases more rapidly as the warming scenario becomes more severe (Figure 6), as the precipitation changes phase from solid to liquid. The inter-GCM spread for liquid precipitation does not change much between the beginning and end of the simulation in all scenarios except RCP8.5, which shows a greater spread towards the end of the simulation (Figure 6). Since RCP8.5 is the most severe, and thus most different, climate change scenario

compared to the present, it is expected that GCMs would have a more difficult time projecting glacier change and consequently projections would be more uncertain.

Compared to liquid precipitation on the glacier area, melt on and off glacier have substantially lower uncertainties in GCM projections, which is supported by Figure 6. This is particularly important for the research goal of this thesis, as it suggests that the variability that is seen in total annual runoff is a result of uncertainty in liquid precipitation—and by extension, uncertainty in projections of individual climate models—rather than glacier melt, which shows more inter-GCM agreement. This indicates that the most effective way to improve runoff projections from glacier models is to improve precipitation schemes in the forcing climate models—an actionable focus for future research efforts.

4.3 Projections of seasonal runoff show decrease in glacier melt, increase in runoff uncertainty

Seasonal runoff projections across the simulated period show high inter-GCM variation in the timing and amplitude of runoff peaks and low inter-GCM variation in dry season lows (Figure 8). At the beginning of the simulation, the shoulder months between the wet and dry seasons—April to May, August to September—have higher quantities of projected runoff in all RCP scenarios compared to later in the simulation, suggesting that the runoff source may be changing. In a comparison of GCM seasonal projections of total runoff for different years, I found that GCM projections agree on average runoff values for dry months but vary substantially in both timing and amplitude in the wet season, which is important for downstream communities, particularly as seasonal rainfall is projected to become more variable (Arias et al., 2021).

Like the spread of GCM values for annual runoff, it appears that the spread of projected seasonal runoff by GCM is dominated by liquid precipitation uncertainty (Figure 9).

Components of seasonal runoff show very few differences by RCP but change significantly between the start and end of the simulation. In a comparison of the relative importance of each component at the beginning of the simulation (Figure 10), I found that liquid precipitation is the most important component in the wet season and that melt on glacier is the most important component during the dry season, suggesting that glacier melt sustains annual runoff in the beginning of the simulation. This is consistent with the findings of Soruco et al., 2015, who found that glaciers provided 27% of La Paz city's dry season water resources between 1963 and 2006. Elsewhere in the semi-arid Andes, glaciers provide up to 59% of dry-season runoff (Ayala et al., 2020). The significance of this dry-season water source further underscores the necessity of improved projections for planning purposes.

At the end of the simulation, melt on and off glacier have almost completely disappeared, and in the dry season melt off glacier has taken over as the most important component to runoff (Figure 9). It is, however, worth noting that while the contribution of melt off glacier is more important than liquid precipitation at the end of the simulation (Figure 10), there is almost no runoff coming from the glacier area, and thus the contributions of all components are almost non-existent. As was found on an annual scale, the growing importance of liquid precipitation as a seasonal runoff source compared to reliable melt on glaciers will have significant impacts on the water resources of La Paz.

4.4 Implications for La Paz and El Alto

The results of this thesis show that runoff to La Paz and El Alto, and thus the cities' water resources, will be significantly impacted by glacier melt, with the most change occurring within the next 30 years. The negative trend in glacier volume projected by my model corresponds with

work done by Soruco and others (2015), who determined that glacier extent decreased between 1963 and 2006 yet that glacier melt continued to sustain societally consequential runoff despite the decline in glacier volume. This thesis suggests that the latter trend will not continue beyond the next 30 years, and that the continued loss of glacier mass will almost completely eliminate the contribution of glacier melt to runoff by 2100. As such, the decrease in total runoff will provide less water to the cities downstream. This will be particularly important as the cities experience higher rates of population growth (United Nations, 2022).

Although runoff will be sustained to some extent by liquid precipitation, the inter-GCM projections of liquid precipitation from my model show substantial variability in the future (Figure 6). Thus, uncertainty in precipitation projections will pose difficulties for future planning. This is important because precipitation is particularly variable on an annual scale, especially during decadal oscillations like El Niño (IPCC, 2021). Intrinsic annual variability in rainfall, as seen in the substantial year-to-year differences in GCM projections, as well as anticipated decadal fluctuations caused by ENSO events, will significantly affect the quantity of runoff to La Paz on an annual scale, especially since the contributions of surrounding glaciers to runoff will be minimal or nonexistent.

The loss of melt on glacier over the simulated period suggests that less water will be available during the dry season and that most seasonal runoff will come from liquid precipitation during the wet season, between January and March (Figure 9). The decline in runoff will pose challenges for agricultural productivity (Lozano-Povis et al., 2021; Vergara et al., 2007) and will have implications for hydropower surrounding La Paz, as the energy output will decrease as the glacier contribution disappears (Vergara et al., 2007; Bradley et al., 2006).

As annual precipitation variability becomes more extreme, as projected by the IPCC, La Paz will need improved strategies for adaptation to seasonal and annual precipitation fluxes. One such strategy may be to ensure existing water reservoirs and storage facilities are prepared for annual variability and high-intensity wet season influx, which could be used as a water resource during the dry season (Kinouchi et al., 2019; Rangecroft et al., 2013).

4.5 Implications for understanding precipitation uncertainty

The driving research goal of this thesis is to address uncertainties in glacier runoff quantification by simulating how annual and seasonal glacier runoff in La Paz responds to uncertainty in future precipitation. Precipitation uncertainty, as determined by differences in GCM projections, has little impact on glacier mass loss, as it is likely that these glaciers would continue to lose mass even if current climate remained constant (Figure 4; Mernild et al., 2013). Additionally, there is relatively little spread in GCM projections for both melt on and off glacier, suggesting that glacier change is a relatively well understood part of the problem (Figure 6, 9).

However, GCM projections of total runoff on an annual and seasonal scale do not agree (Figure 5). This is due to the large spread of GCM projections for liquid precipitation (Figure 6, 9). The results of this thesis suggest that uncertainty in precipitation forcing, determined by the ten GCMs used in this study, results in large uncertainties in total annual and seasonal runoff (see Figure 5, 6, 8, & 9). As such, the variability that we see in total runoff seems to derive itself from the variability of precipitation projections rather than from differences in glacier melt. This supports evidence from previous literature that, in order for glacier models to project runoff more accurately, climate models for high-mountain regions should be improved to better project precipitation and other climate characteristics (Marzeion et al., 2020; Buytaert et al., 2010).

4.6 Project limitations

The results of this thesis show that a significant amount of glacial runoff to La Paz, Bolivia, comes from liquid precipitation, rather than from melting of glacier ice or snow. The quantity of liquid precipitation projected is surprising compared to other studies, especially since the glaciers within the Cordillera Real exist between 4000 and 6400 meters above sea level. Previous studies have suggested that high quantities of precipitation in a liquid state would not be expected above 5000 meters a.s.l., although the occurrence of high-altitude liquid precipitation in the future may increase as temperature increases in the tropics (Perry et al., 2017; Soruco et al., 2015). The high quantities of projected liquid precipitation produced by my model are likely results of the poor resolution of topography by climate models and also of the glacier model's temperature calibration method. OGGM, as well as most well-known glacier models, uses the temperature-index melt model to determine a temperature bias for the simulated glacier (Marzeion et al., 2020; Maussion et al., 2019). The calculation of this bias often depends on the availability of in-situ measurements to which the model may be compared for accuracy (Maussion et al., 2019). In-situ glacier measurements within Bolivia are limited, and thus make the bias calculation less accurate within low latitudes (Gärtner-Roer et al., 2019). Additionally, the temperature index melt model used by these glacier models does not capture well the processes that are important for the surface energy balance of tropical glaciers, and as such, poor performance within the low latitudes can be expected (Marzeion et al., 2012; Rabatel et al., 2013). Thus, the high quantities of liquid precipitation projected by my model are results of a broader challenge with the capacity for models to calibrate to temperatures within the low latitudes.

In addition to their limitations regarding precipitation phase changes, glacier models struggle to capture important processes such as seasonality and sublimation in their calculations of surface mass balance of tropical glaciers. The mass balances of glaciers within the Cordillera Real are significantly affected by sublimation, which is not included as a parameter within most large-scale glacier models (Wagnon et al., 1999; Marzeion et al., 2020). Moreover, the seasonality of Bolivia's climate, and that of low-latitude climates, is markedly different from the seasonality of mid-latitude regions, with two or three seasons usually defined as 'wet' and 'dry' compared to four distinct seasons (Soruco et al., 2015). Since most glacier models are developed and tested on mid- to high-latitude glaciers—which exist in four-season climates—there are limitations in the ways that low-latitude glaciers can be modeled (Huss & Hock, 2015; Maussion et al., 2019; Rabatel et al., 2013).

Finally, this project does not fully sample the wide range of possible future precipitation values. For this project, I used different GCM projections of precipitation, which have a range of values, to simulate precipitation variability, but do not fully map the distribution of possible future precipitation between those simulated values. It is possible to modify precipitation using a scaling factor within OGGM; however, the use of a multiplicative factor assumes a statistical structure that may not be representative, and a study based on modifying the precipitation factor would be more descriptive of glacier-model calibration than of uncertainties arising from forcing data.

4.7 Possible future work

This project has introduced numerous questions and potential future analyses, which include direct manipulation of the model and its input as well as expanding the study area. In

order to map precipitation uncertainty more accurately, it would be important to expand the number of GCMs studied to perform a more comprehensive statistical analysis of uncertainty, or to create synthetic time series of precipitation using statistical methods to use as input to the model (Ultee, Robel, & Castruccio, 2023 preprint). To address the precipitation phase change anomaly identified in section 4.6, future work might include direct modification of the temperature bias within OGGM or modification of the temperature lapse rate, which is by default 6.5 C km^{-1} but could be expected to be closer to the dry lapse rate high altitudes of $9.8^\circ \text{ C km}^{-1}$ (Maussion et al., 2019; Hemond & Fechner, 2023). Future work might also build off the study by Soruco and others (2015) by determining the percent contribution of runoff to La Paz's water resources using hydrologic discharge data for the cities. Furthermore, the runoff data output from my model could be analyzed on an individual basin scale to best identify sub-catchment-scale runoff sources. Finally, my adaptation of OGGM could potentially be used for a larger, regional analysis of runoff evolution.

CHAPTER 5: CONCLUSION

In this project, I adapted and executed the Open Global Glacier Model using 10 global climate models to project runoff for La Paz and El Alto, Bolivia from 2020 to 2100. I found that the greatest uncertainties in estimates of annual and seasonal runoff result from uncertainties in climate models rather than from RCP scenarios. Additionally, the greatest uncertainties among runoff components come from uncertainties in precipitation, rather than from glacier melt. My model projects for glacier runoff to decrease substantially within the next 30 years, reaching a point at which runoff is almost entirely sourced from liquid precipitation. Seasonal runoff is also projected to change, with less available water in the dry season and its shoulder months (April-October) due to an almost complete loss of melt from the glacier. For La Paz, this means that water resources will become increasingly dependent on wet season (November-March) precipitation, which is projected to become more variable in the coming decades. Since modeled uncertainties in runoff projections stem from uncertainties in climate model precipitation outputs, climate models for high mountain regions should be improved to better project precipitation. Future work might focus on scaling the temperature factor within the glacier model to better predict precipitation phase changes as well as creating a synthetic time series of precipitation using statistical methods to fully map the distribution of possible future precipitation.

SUPPLEMENTARY ELECTRONIC INFORMATION

All electronic information, including the python scripts for OGGM model adaption/execution and the python scripts for analysis, can be found in my GitHub repository [DOI: 10.5281/zenodo.7926084]. It can be accessed and used by anyone. Please contact the author (Molly Arndt, mollyjarndt@gmail.com) with any questions.

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